

Schema-Aware Query Routing with Temperature Classification and AI Workload Detection

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27 March 2026

Publication Type: Defensive Publication – Prior Art Disclosure

Classification: cs.DB (Databases)

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DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.19244540

Abstract

We present a schema-aware query routing system for database proxies that automatically classifies tables by data temperature (HOT/WARM/COLD based on inter-query arrival times) and workload type (OLTP/OLAP/Vector based on query structure), detects AI-specific workloads (RAG retrieval, embedding batch inserts, agent conversation patterns), and routes queries to optimal backend nodes using a learning classifier that adapts table classifications from observed access patterns without manual configuration. The system includes automatic schema discovery via `information_schema` queries, shard key detection from index analysis, and relationship-aware routing that co-locates related table queries. While database proxies with routing exist (Vitess vschema, ProxySQL regex rules, Citus distribution columns), none combine automatic temperature classification, AI workload detection, and an adaptive learning classifier in a single system.

Keywords: Schema Routing, Query Classification, Temperature-Based Routing, AI Workload Detection, Learning Classifier, Adaptive Routing

1 Background and Prior Art

Vitess (vtgate): Routes based on manually-configured vschema definitions mapping tables to keyspaces and shards. No automatic classification, no temperature awareness, no AI workload detection.

ProxySQL: Rule-based routing using regex matching on query text. Manual rule configuration. No schema awareness, no automatic learning.

CockroachDB Range Routing: Automatic range-based routing internal to the database. Not a proxy feature, not configurable by workload type.

Citus: Shard-based routing for PostgreSQL requiring explicit distribution column declarations via `create_distributed_table()`. Schema modifications required.

Amazon Aurora Read Replicas: Application-level routing (connection string specifies reader/writer endpoint). No automatic workload classification.

2 Technical Contribution

2.1 Dual-Dimension Table Classification

```

1 enum DataTemperature {
2     Hot,    // inter-query interval < 1 second
3     Warm,  // inter-query interval < 1 minute
4     Cold,  // inter-query interval > 1 minute
5 }
6
7 enum WorkloadType {
8     Oltp,   // point lookups, short transactions, high concurrency
9     Olap,   // aggregations, full scans, long queries
10    Vector, // similarity search, embedding operations
11    Mixed,  // combination of above
12 }

```

Temperature is computed from exponentially weighted moving average of inter-query arrival times per table. Workload type is inferred from query structure analysis: point lookups (WHERE pk = ?) indicate OLTP, GROUP BY/aggregation functions indicate OLAP, vector distance functions indicate Vector.

2.2 AI Workload Detection

The QueryClassifier identifies AI-specific access patterns:

- **RAG queries:** Vector similarity search (ORDER BY vector <-> ?) followed by text column retrieval within the same session, within a short time window
- **Embedding batch inserts:** Multiple INSERT statements with vector columns in rapid succession
- **Agent conversations:** Repeated parameterized queries with varying parameters but identical structure, characteristic of tool-use patterns in AI agents

```

1 struct RagAnalytics {
2     retrieval_count: u64,
3     avg_retrieval_latency: Duration,
4     avg_chunks_retrieved: f64,
5     generation_count: u64,
6 }

```

2.3 Learning Classifier

```

1 struct LearningClassifier {
2     history: DashMap<String, QueryHistory>, // per-table query history
3     model: Arc<RwLock<ClassificationModel>>, // current classifications
4     schema: Arc<SchemaRegistry>, // for updates
5 }

```

The classifier observes query executions and periodically (configurable interval, default 5 minutes) re-computes table classifications. No manual configuration or schema annotations required. The classification model uses:

- Inter-query arrival time distribution for temperature
- Query structure histogram for workload type
- Session correlation for AI pattern detection

2.4 Routing Decision Matrix

2.5 Automatic Schema Discovery

SchemaDiscovery queries `information_schema.tables`, `information_schema.columns`, and `information_schema.statistics` to build the initial SchemaRegistry. Refresh interval configurable (default 5 minutes). Detects new tables, dropped tables, and index changes automatically.

Temperature + Workload	Query Type	Routing Target
HOT + OLTP	Point lookups	Low-latency SSD node, connection pooling
HOT + Vector	Similarity search	SIMD-optimized or GPU node
WARM + OLAP	Analytics	High-memory, high-throughput node
COLD + OLAP	Historical queries	Archive/cold storage node
Any + RAG	Multi-step retrieval	Vector node + text node (fan-out)

3 Implementation

Implemented in Rust. Module: `schema_routing/` with sub-modules: `registry.rs` (SchemaRegistry, TableSchema, ColumnSchema), `analyzer.rs` (query analysis), `router.rs` (routing decisions), `classifier.rs` (LearningClassifier), `discovery.rs` (schema auto-discovery), `metrics.rs`, `admin.rs` (runtime configuration API). Total: 368+ LOC in mod.rs. Licensed under SSPL-1.0.